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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION AMONG EXECUTIVES AND SUPERVISORS OF PRIVATE SECTOR INDUSTRY: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

Dr. (Mrs) Meenu Kumar¹ and Dr. Shakti Prakash²

Abstract

Extensive research has been conducted in the area of work motivation and satisfaction as it affects not only productivity but also organizational commitments of employees. The present study focuses on comparison of job satisfaction among executives and supervisors on six dimensions of job- working conditions and basic amenities at work place ,pay and other monetary benefits, work environment & Interpersonal relation, work itself, growth opportunities and recognition, management policies and their commitment. The research methodology used for the study is the survey methodology. The result indicates that supervisors scores more on every dimensions, and they are more satisfied than supervisors except on growth opportunity and recognition on which both are equally satisfied.

INTRODUCTION:

Job satisfaction of employees is one of the most important aspect of work place as it not only affects the employees well being but the organization is also suffered if they are dissatisfied. Satisfaction leads to better productivity, accomplishment of organizational goals and

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